

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

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No. 37

• France

Co-occurrence of two *Alexandrium* species in Thau Lagoon

The occurrence of *Alexandrium* species involved in paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) in Thau lagoon (French Mediterranean) (Fig. 1) is known since 1998 [1-2]. Blooms usually occur in spring and autumn, and cause economic damage to shellfish farming that represents 10% of national production. Maximal vegetative cell densities reached 4.5×10^6 cell L⁻¹ and 16×10^6 cell L⁻¹ in October 2003 and November 2004 respectively. Such cell concentrations resulted in red tides during these periods (Fig. 2). Regarding species identification, thecal plate observations and the detection of complex toxin profiles in natural populations sampled in 1998 originally suggested the co-existence of *Alexandrium tamarense* and *Alexandrium catenella* [2]. These

Fig. 1. Thau lagoon is located 30 km southwest of Montpellier (Hérault, South France). Shellfish farming sectors (dashed lines) represent 1/5 of total surface of the lagoon.

suspicions were confirmed by recent observations that some cells were characterized by unusual size and morphology (Fig. 3).

For a clarification, during blooms in 2007, more than 400 monoclonal strains were established by single cell isolation

from seawater samples collected in the creek of l'Angle (NE part of lagoon, Fig. 2). Following genomic DNA extraction, the ribotype of ≈ 200 *Alexandrium* sp. Strains, originating from both spring and autumn 2007 blooms, was resolved by
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• Brazil

Ostreopsis ovata blooms on Rio de Janeiro coast

There are sporadic reports of the occurrence of the epiphytic-benthic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis ovata* on the Brazilian coast. *Ostreopsis* sp. strains were isolated from São Sebastião channel, São Paulo State (23°46'S, 45°21'W) in 2001 [1]. In summer 1998/1999 and 2001/2002, *O. ovata* blooms were reported in Arraial do Cabo (22°59' S, 42°00' W), in Rio de Janeiro State. In 1998, a biofilm of *O. ovata* cells was seen covering epilithic macroalgae [2-3]. *O. ovata* blooms were associated with sea urchins (*Echinometra lucunter*) deaths, and palytoxin analogues were identified in extracts from the *O. ovata* natural

population [2]. In November 1998 two human deaths occurred as a consequence of seafood poisoning in Cabo Frio City, near Arraial do Cabo, but it was not clear if they were linked to the *O. ovata* bloom [2].

In Santa Catarina, on the southern Brazilian coast (27°16'S, 48°19'W), high *O. ovata* abundance (10^5 cells L⁻¹) was associated in January 2004 with a *Trichodesmium erythraeum* (Cyanobacteria) bloom and attached to the benthic diatom *Licmophora* sp. [4]. In March 2006, *Ostreopsis ovata* and *Prorocentrum lima* were the dominant species associated with macroalgae in Pernambuco, in the Brazilian northeast

(8°32'S, 35°00'W) [5].

A project aiming to identify and quantify epibenthic dinoflagellates associated with macroalgae on the eastern Rio de Janeiro coast and to investigate community dynamics was established in June 2006. The study area is characterized by rocky shores covered by granite boulders, ending in a sand bottom with no influence from rivers (Fig. 1). A survey in a broader area was performed at 10 stations along the eastern Rio de Janeiro coast in summer 2007 and two sampling stations were monitored from June 2006 and throughout 2007 (Nascimento *et al.*, in
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sequencing the (ITS1-5.8SrDNA-ITS2) nuclear ribosomal DNA region.

Results revealed the presence of two ribotypes in Thau lagoon seawater: the formerly known "Temperate Asia" *A. catenella* and the "Western European" *A. tamarensis*, in proportions of 44/56 in spring and 70/30 in autumn. Such co-occurrence in natural populations has been reported from Scottish coastal waters, i.e. *A. tamarensis* vs. *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* [3]. However, in mixed phytoplankton assemblages *Alexandrium* species are difficult to distinguish. To settle this matter, a rapid and selective method was developed to identify the two species isolated from field samples; it consists of a semi-multiplex allele specific PCR using ribotype-specific primers. These newly designed primers lead to the specific amplification of a PCR product that has a different size in each species, thus enabling rapid identification based on amplicon length.

Several questions remain unanswered and require further investigations. When did *A. tamarensis* colonize Thau lagoon? How can we explain the co-occurrence of two *Alexandrium* species also observed in Temperate Asia and Western Europe respectively? Are the dates and vectors of introduction similar? For investigating

Fig. 2. Graph shows changes in cell density of *Alexandrium* sp. blooms in Angle Creek, Thau lagoon with time. Background photography shows red tide during bloom of *Alexandrium* sp.

the origin of *A. catenella*, population genetic investigation is in process using microsatellite markers. Microsatellite markers are also developed to investigate *A. tamarensis* origin and, maybe, its mechanism of introduction. The analysis of strains derived from cyst-germination from stored sediments collected since 2002 might supply useful information about the successive colonizations.

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B. Genovesi¹, E. Masseret¹, M-S. Shin-Grzebyk¹, D. Grzebyk¹, P. Berrebi², P-A. Gagnaire², M. Laabir¹, Y. Collos¹, A. Pastoureaud³ & A. Vaquer¹

¹Université Montpellier 2, UMR 5119 UM2-CNRS-IFREMER Ecosystèmes Lagunaires, équipe Efflorescences Toxiques et Diversité Algale, Montpellier, France. Email: benjamin.genovesi@gmail.com; estelle.masseret@univ-montp2.fr; yves.collos@univ-montp2.fr

²Université Montpellier 2, UMR 5554 Institut des Sciences de l'Évolution, équipe Génétique et Environnement-Métapopulations, Conservation et Co-évolution, Montpellier, France.

³IFREMER Laboratoire Environnement Ressources/LR, BP 171, 34203 Sète, France.

Fig. 3. Vegetative cells of *Alexandrium* sp. from 2007 blooms cultivated in laboratory: single-cell (A), 2 cell- (B) and 4 cell-chains (C) observed in *Alexandrium catenella* strains; single-cell (D) and 2 cell-chain (E) observed in *Alexandrium tamarensis* strains.

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prep.). A number of potentially toxic dinoflagellates were identified on macroalgae surfaces, such as *O. ovata*, *P. lima*, *Prorocentrum emarginatum*, *Prorocentrum rhathymum*, *Coolia* cf. *monotis* and *Amphidinium* cf. *operculatum*. The identification and quantification of dinoflagellate cells in macroalgae samples was performed in a counting chamber on an inverted microscope and taxonomic confirmation was performed under epifluorescence using calcofluor dye.

In the first 6 months of the study, two *O. ovata* (Fig. 2) blooms were recorded in the region. The first event occurred in June 2006 at Búzios, when *O. ovata* and *P. lima* were found associated with the macroalgae *Laurencia* sp., *Amphiroa fragillissima* (Rhodophyta), *Sargassum vulgare* (Phaeophyta) and *Codium intertextum* (Chlorophyta). *O. ovata* densities reached 1.5×10^5 cells g⁻¹ fresh weight (FW) (1.2×10^6 cells g⁻¹ dry weight) of *Laurencia* sp. (Table 1). Mean *O. ovata* densities in *S. vulgare* (n=3) samples was 7.2×10^4 cells g⁻¹ FW of macroalgae (5.1×10^5 cells g⁻¹ dry weight). In *C. intertextum* lower densities were registered, of 1.7×10^3 cells g⁻¹ FW (1.6×10^4 cells g⁻¹ dry weight). *P. lima* was also observed on macroalgae samples, in densities that varied between 100 and 1302 cells g⁻¹ FW (Table 1).

At the Forno embayment in Arraial do Cabo, a yellowish-brown biofilm was seen covering the epilithic algae community on 5 December 2006 (Fig.

Fig. 1. Eastern Rio de Janeiro coast (Brazil) and location of sampling sites.

3a). At this time, *O. ovata* densities reached 2.1×10^4 cells g⁻¹ FW in a mixed sample of *A. fragillissima* and *Jania capillacea* (Rhodophyta). Rocky shores at the Forno station are dominated by coralline red algae such as *A. fragillissima*, *Amphiroa brasiliensis*, *Amphiroa beauvoisii* and *J. capillacea*. *P. lima* was not observed in samples during the *O. ovata* bloom. Although samples from other places along the coast were not analyzed at that time, it is likely that the *O. ovata* bloom was widespread through a larger area, as the biofilm was also observed covering macroalgae in a nearby embayment on 27 November 2006 (Fig. 3b).

O. ovata densities at the Forno embayment two weeks before the bloom (21 November 2006) ranged between 24 cells g⁻¹ FW on *J. capillacea* and 392 cells g⁻¹ FW on *A. fragillissima*. Warm (average air temperature 24.1 °C) and calm (average wind speed 4.5 m s⁻¹, 8.6 mm of rain) weather conditions that prevailed

between 21 November and 5 December 2006 provided optimal conditions for bloom formation.

Early in 2007, intense rainfall (105.4 mm) and strong winds (mean of 7.6 m s⁻¹ with gusts of 19.4 m s⁻¹) that occurred between 1 and 5 January 2007 caused a marked decrease in *O. ovata* densities. Moreover, the Arraial do Cabo region is characterized by a coastal upwelling [6] and such an event was recorded in 9 January 2007, contributing to surface cooling. On 23 January 2007, *O. ovata* maximum density at Forno embayment was 1,337 cells g⁻¹ FW on *A. fragillissima*; on this occasion, *P. lima* was observed at densities between 30 and 230 cells g⁻¹ FW on *A. fragillissima* and *P. emarginatum* and *A. cf. operculatum* were also recorded in lower densities.

O. ovata densities on the eastern Rio de Janeiro coast are among the highest reported in the literature. Vila *et al.* [7] recorded peak densities of *Ostreopsis* sp. to be 5.9×10^5 cells g⁻¹ FW in *Halopteris scoparina* during July 1997 on the Catalan coast (Spain), and Aligizaki & Nikolaidis [8] reported maximum *Ostreopsis* densities of 4.0×10^5 cells g⁻¹ FW on the North Aegean coast (Greece). The highest density of *O. lenticularis* was estimated to be 2.3×10^5 cells g⁻¹ FW in *Dictyota* at Laurel Reef, Puerto Rico (Ballantine *et al.*, 1985) while in Hawaii the highest *Ostreopsis* sp. density was 1.8×10^4 cells g⁻¹ FW in *Pterocladia capillacea* in November 2001 [9].

O. ovata cells were isolated and cultures are currently being kept in the laboratory for further work. *Ostreopsis* species are known to produce putative

Fig. 2. *Ostreopsis ovata* cells from Búzios. (A) Light microscopy, (B) Epifluorescence with calcofluor. Scale bars = 10 μ m.

Fig. 3. Biofilm of *Ostreopsis ovata* covering the red algae *Amphiroa fragilissima* (A) at Forno embayment on 5 December 2006 and (B) at Cabo Frio Island on 27 November 2006.

palytoxin. Toxin analyses of a strain of *O. ovata* isolated from the Rio de Janeiro coast have shown the presence of palytoxin analogues [10]. Two *O. ovata* strains isolated during the current study showed haemolytic activity that was inhibited by ouabain (unpublished data). Palytoxin was confirmed as the causative agent in human seafood poisoning through the consumption of crabs and fish [11–12]. Moreover, over the last few years *Ostreopsis* species, mainly *O. ovata*, were involved in the intoxication of people who were exposed to marine aerosols along the Italian coast. Symptoms reported included rhinorrhoea, bronchoconstriction, coughing, fever and dermatitis [13].

On the eastern Rio de Janeiro coast, aquaculture activities (particularly the mussel *Perna perna*), have been expanding in recent years, and fisheries and tourism are important for the local economy. These activities are

vulnerable to the impacts of harmful algae blooms in the area, and considering the potential of this phenomenon, a project has begun to study the seasonal dynamics of epibenthic dinoflagellates associated with macroalgae in the region.

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S. Mattos Nascimento¹, P. Oliveira Monteiro¹, C.E. Leite Ferreira² & E. González-Rodríguez²

¹Laboratório de Ciências Ambientais (LCA), Universidade Estadual do Norte Fluminense (UENF). Av. Alberto Lamego, 2000, 28.013-602, Campos, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Email: silvia.nascimento@gmail.com

²Instituto de Estudos do Mar Almirante Paulo Moreira (IEAPM), R. Kioto, 253, Praia dos Anjos, 28.930-000 Arraial do Cabo, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Email: eliane@ieapm.mar.mil.br

Table 1. *Ostreopsis ovata* and *Prorocentrum lima* absolute ($n = 1$) or average ($n = 2$ or 3) densities (cells g^{-1} FW) in macroalgae samples from Búzios and Arraial do Cabo, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Búzios, 10/06/2006		
	<i>Ostreopsis ovata</i>	<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>
<i>Laurencia</i> sp. (n=1)	151,420	1,302
<i>Sargassum vulgare</i> (n=3)	71,630	936
<i>Amphiroa fragilissima</i> (n=1)	33,184	735
<i>Codium intertextum</i> (n=2)	1,689	100
Arraial do Cabo, 5/12/2006		
	<i>Ostreopsis ovata</i>	<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>
<i>Amphiroa fragilissima</i> + <i>Jania capillacea</i> (n=2)	13,114	0

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• Mexico

First record of *Cochlodinium fulvescens* in Mexican Pacific

At the beginning of March 2008, a *Cochlodinium* bloom occurred in Bahía de Mazatlán, Sinaloa, México (23°11'11.8" N, 106°26'46.2" W, Fig. 1). To study this event, surface samples were collected and fixed with Lugol's solution. Some natural aliquots were reserved for taxonomical identification and culture establishment. Fixed samples were used to determine phytoplankton composition and *Cochlodinium* abundance.

At first we supposed that the bloom was caused by *C. polykrikoides*, but with the isolated material, we observed that coloration, shape and morphology of the cells and chains, and specially the intermediate position of the sulcus between the semicircular cingulum at the dorsal side (Fig. 2b), match the recently described *Cochlodinium fulvescens* [1]. In culture, paired cells or chains of 4 and 8 cells developed (Fig. 2). In dorsal view, the sulcus and a reddish orange pigmented body were easily observable (Fig. 2c). Cell shape was sub-spherical to ellipsoidal, the

epitheca was hemispherical, and the hypotheca with the posterior end was slightly excavated by the sulcal groove. Mean length and width were 41.3 μm and 37.2 μm ($n = 30$), respectively. In field samples four cell chains were observed, but the addition of the Lugol's solution promotes breaking of the chain into pairs.

Average *C. fulvescens* population density ranged from 3.8×10^5 to 4.9×10^5 cells L^{-1} , and appeared with a bloom of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. (1.7×10^6 to 4×10^6 cells L^{-1}). The bloom was also included other dinoflagellates such as *Ceratium furca* (1.3×10^5 cells L^{-1}), and *C. balechii* (1.1×10^4 cells L^{-1}). No adverse effects were observed during the bloom.

Until now, only 7 species of *Cochlodinium* had been recorded in the Mexican Pacific: *C. catenatum*, *C. citron*, *C. faurei*, *C. cf. miniatum*, *C. pirum*, and *C. polykrikoides* [2]. *Cochlodinium catenatum* and *C. polykrikoides* are the most important because of the harmful blooms recorded

Fig. 1. Location of *Cochlodinium fulvescens* bloom in Bahía de Mazatlán, Sinaloa (Mexico).

in Bahía Banderas [3] and Bahía de La Paz [4, 5]. The isolation and culture procedures led to the first detection in the Mexican Pacific of the chain forming *Cochlodinium fulvescens*. Bahía de Mazatlán is one of the most important areas with frequent red tides (both harmful and innocuous), and where the historic record is the most extended and accurate [6]. No previous evidence of *Cochlodinium* species morphologically similar to *C. fulvescens* was found.

Cochlodinium fulvescens occurs in the Seto Inland Sea (Japan), Hurun Bay (Indonesia), British Columbia (Canada), and California (USA) [1, 7, 8]. The phylogenetic tree inferred from partial (D1-D6 regions) LSU rDNA sequences clearly differentiated between *C. polykrikoides* and *C. fulvescens*; however, these species are closely related as a sister group [8]. In addition the morphology of the chain forming dinoflagellates of this genus is very similar [7]; it is therefore possible that *C. fulvescens* on the Mexican Pacific coast had been identified previously as *C. polykrikoides* or *C. catenatum*.

If we succeed with culture establishment, considering that *C. fulvescens* in Canada has been reported as a red tide forming dinoflagellate related to substantial mortalities of farmed salmon [9], we will corroborate the ichthyotoxic properties and life cycle.

Fig. 2. Light micrographs of *Cochlodinium fulvescens*. (A) chain of four cells, (B) chain of two cells; arrowheads indicate sulcus position, (C) dorsal view showing the reddish orange pigmented body. Scale=20 μm .

• Mexico

Myrionecta, *Gyrodinium* and *Katodinium* bloom in Gulf of California

Plate 1. (1) *Katodinium glaucum*, (2) *Myrionecta rubra*, (3) *Gyrodinium instriatum*, (4) *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, (5) *Gymnodinium catenatum*, (6) *Torodinium robustum*, (7) *Gyrodinium falcatum*, (8) *Gyrodinium spirale*, (9) *Gyrodinium dominans*, (10) *Gonyaulax polygramma*, (11) *Gyrodinium* sp., (12) *Protoperidinium* sp. feeding on the diatom *Thalassiosira* sp., (13) *Warnowia polyphemus*, (14) *Warnowia violescens*, (15) *Licmophora* on a copepod tail, (16) cyst of *Polykrikos* sp.

Microalgae blooms are frequent and periodic throughout the year in Bahía de La Paz, part of the southwestern Gulf of California. This bay has experienced frequent blooms, especially since 1984; more than 40 blooms and 25 bloom-forming taxa have been identified here [1, 2]. Bloom-forming species belong to different phytoplankton groups: dinoflagellates, diatoms, raphidophytes, planktonic cyanobacteria, and the ciliate *Myrionecta rubra*. This study describes a two-day multi-species bloom that occurred near the sandbar ‘El Mogote’ that separates the shallow lagoon from the main bay. On 17–18 June 2008, red patches appeared near El Mogote in Bahía de La Paz; (Sample A; 24°10.7’N, 110°22.09’W; Sample B; 24°11.1’N, 110°21.90’W). Samples were taken with a plastic bucket and preserved with Lugol’s solution. Another sub-sample was taken for live phytoplankton analysis. Sea surface temperature was recorded. Ciliate and phytoplankton abundance were estimated and species identified in sedimentation chambers under an inverted microscope. Live samples of the red tides were used for identification of naked dinoflagellates.

A total of 45 microalgae species and

one ciliate were identified. Dinoflagellates were by far the most abundant group in abundance and species richness (30 taxa). They were followed by diatoms (12), silicoflagellates (2) and lebridian (Table 1 lists the more abundant taxa). The total density (phytoplankton and the ciliate) at the sampling stations was similar on both days, varying between 4.97×10^6 cells L^{-1} on the first and 4.25×10^6 cells L^{-1} on the second day. The ciliate *Myrionecta rubra* and the two naked dinoflagellates *Gyrodinium instriatum* and *Katodinium glaucum* were the most abundant bloom species (Table 1, Plate 1). Highest numbers the first day were *M. rubra* (3.42×10^6 cells L^{-1}), *G. instriatum* (98×10^3 cells L^{-1}) and *K. glaucum* (41×10^3 cells L^{-1}). A shift in the dominant species occurred during the second day with highest numbers of *G. instriatum* (3.24×10^6 cells L^{-1}), *K. glaucum* (620×10^3 cells L^{-1}) and *Myrionecta rubra* (160×10^3 cells L^{-1}). Previous blooms of *G. instriatum* have occurred in this bay at the end of summer and linked to breakdown of the thermocline. *M. rubra* red tides are common during the upwelling season (2). *K. glaucum* is normally solitary, however two cell chains were found; this is an easily recognizable species in

live and lugol fixed samples. No previous blooms of *K. glaucum* have been reported in the Gulf of California. Other

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L. Morquecho. CIBNOR, Mar Bermejo 195, Col. Playa Palo de Sta. Rita, La Paz, B.C.S. 23090, Mexico.

Email: lamorquecho@cibnor.mx

R. Alonso-Rodríguez, Unidad Académica de Mazatlán, Instituto de Ciencias del Mar y Limnología, UNAM, Av. Joel Montes Camarena s/n 82240, Mazatlán, Sin., Mexico. Email: rosalba@ola.icmyl.unam.mx

naked dinoflagellates such as *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, *C. fulvescens*, *Gyrodinium spirale* and *Torodinium robustum* were also collected. *K. glaucum*, *Warnowia violescens*, *C. fulvescens* and *T. robustum* are reported for the first time in Bahía de La Paz. *Amphidinium acutissimum*, *C. fulvescens*, *Ebria tripartita*, *Gyrodinium dominans*, *G. pepo*, *W. polyphemus* and unidentified *Gyrodinium* species are the first reports from the Gulf of California. Identification of live samples was an opportunity to observe several mixotrophs (such as *Protopteridinium* spp.) feeding on *Thalassiosira* sp. (Plate 1, Fig. 12). One of the most common dinoflagellate predators along the coasts of Baja California Peninsula is *Noctiluca scintillans* [3], recently observed feeding on *G. catenatum* (chains of 4–16 cells per *Noctiluca* cell) in Bahía de Los Angeles, Bahía Concepción, and Bahía de La Paz which are large bays in the Gulf of California. Large (>20 µm) naked and thecate heterotrophic dinoflagellates may form large biomasses in response to spring blooms of diatoms [4] and dinoflagellate blooms (this study). Other genera of naked heterotrophic dinoflagellates such as *Gyrodinium*, *Polykrikos*, *Pheopolykrikos* and *Warnowia* were observed in the examination of live phytoplankton samples. The importance of the heterotrophic component of marine dinoflagellates has not previously been reported for any area of the Gulf of California. An important finding was the epizotic symbiosis between the diatom *Licmophora* sp. on the copepod carapace.

The bloom occurred under upwelling conditions characteristic of this time period, accompanied by low water temperature (20 to 21°C) and winds of 3.0 to 4.5 m s⁻¹. Upwellings are common events during the late autumn to early spring [5, 6]. However, a short period of upwelling has been reported at the end of spring that is related to the SE winds [7, 8]. Variations in the wind regime from changes in the position and strength of high and low pressure systems cause short-term variability in upwelling-downwelling cycles within

Table 1. Abundance (10³ cells L⁻¹) of microalgae and the ciliate *M. rubra* found in Bahía de La Paz during a two-day bloom in June 2008. Note: The original table has been shortened by omission of less common species. Readers interested in the full list should contact the authors.

	Sample A	Sample B	Sample A	Sample B
CILIATES	17/06/2008	17/06/2008	18/06/2008	18/06/2008
<i>Myrionecta rubra</i>	3420	2850	160	89
DINOFLAGELLATES				
<i>Cochlodinium polykrikoides</i>	12	14	16	22
<i>Gonyaulax polygramma</i>	4	32	36	12
<i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i>	16	12	42	79
<i>Gyrodinium instriatum</i>	980	833	3100	3420
<i>Gyrodinium spirale</i>	1	4	27	2
<i>Karenia c.f. mikitori</i>	10	12	17	13
<i>Katodinium glaucum</i>	414	750	620	560
<i>Pheopolykrikos hartmannii</i>	1	6	35	21
<i>Polykrikos schwartzii</i>	11	9	31	14
<i>Protopteridinium claudicans</i>	4	1	4	60
<i>Torodinium robustum</i>	0	2	6	40
DIATOMS				
<i>Asteromphalus heptactis</i>	8	4	18	20
<i>Hemiaulus sinensis</i>	2	0	10	8
<i>Leptocylindrus danicus</i>	8	4	0	12
<i>Licmophora</i> sp. (on copepod carapace)	0	0	28	0
<i>Pseudo-Nitzschia</i> spp.	6	5	11	14
<i>Rhizosolenia hyalina</i>	20	17	24	17
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp.	3	12	1	2
TOTAL ABUNDANCE	4976	4615	4216	4454

each season [9]. Temperatures are lower than typical (26–28 °C) for this month [6]; however, similar low water temperature (18–21 °C) have been recorded in this month in this area under similar meteorological conditions [7, 8]. In essence, blooms in Bahía de La Paz at this season are regulated by upwelling currents that bring nutrient-enriched water and probably re-suspended dinoflagellate cysts to the surface. Germination of cysts and blooms of phytoplankton are promoted by higher levels of nitrates and phosphates. In our samples, some unidentified dinoflagellate cysts and *Polykrikos* sp. cysts were found. Some species such as *C. polykrikoides*, *G. instriatum*, *G. catenatum*, *G. polygramma*, *L. polyedra*, *P. hartmannii*, *P. kofoidii*, and *P. schwartzii* are cyst-forming dinoflagellates [10]. The presence of cysts and cyst-forming dinoflagellates are related to the upwelling that occurred in the week prior to and during the bloom.

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I. Gárate-Lizárraga*, C.J. Band-Schmidt & T. Grayeb-del Alamo. Centro Interdisciplinario de Ciencias Marinas del Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Apdo. 592, Col. Centro, La Paz, B.C.S. 23000, Mexico. *Email: igarate@ipn.mx

• Mexico

New HAB records in the Gulf of California

In a previous contribution, we reported on HAB's on the surface waters of Mazatlan Bay, Sinaloa, Mexico over the 23 years from 1979 to 2002 [1]. At the time, we mentioned *Scrippsiella trochoidea* and *Prorocentrum dentatum* among the species responsible; we now know these were wrongly identified using light microscopy. Our recent observations of the collections held at the Plankton Laboratory (ICMyL-UNAM, Mazatlan Unit) allow us to examine both dinoflagellates using SEM equipment (JEOL/EO JSM 6360) on previously washed and alcohol dehydrated samples dried at CO₂ critical point (Samdri-795 equipment) and, finally gold covered using a Fine Coat Ion Sputter LFC-1100. The images obtained were appropriate for review the ultrastructure and correctly identify the specimens as *Pentapharsodinium trachodium* Indelicato et Loeblich 1985 [2] and *Prorocentrum donghaiense* Lu 2001 [3], respectively.

P. trachodium have a scrippsielloid shape, 20–36 µm long and 15–28 µm wide (N=64). The plate disposition is orthoperidinioid, with the formula: po, x, 4', 3^a, 7'', 5c (4c+T) 4s, 5''', 2'''' (Fig.1A–D). The Sp plate is short and never reached the cingulum, showing the dorsal apithec al tabulation bipesiod. All plate surfaces with the exception of plate x are covered by small pimples. Also, trichocysts surrounded by circles of five pimples are widely distributed on the plates surfaces (Fig.1D). A gelatinous apical stalk emerges from the apical pore complex (not shown). Blooms always occurred as bright reddish patches.

P. donghaiense is a small elongated cell measuring 16.5–

Fig. 1. *Pentapharsodinium trachodium*. A) epitheca showing plate 1' ortho. B) sulcal plates. C) hypotheca. D) detail of ornamentation of thecal surface, showing difference between the widespread and unorganized pimples and the neatly organized circles surrounding trichocyst pores.

Fig. 2. *Prorocentrum donghaiense*. A-B) left valve showing dorsal elongation. C-D) outer and inner side of valves. Note trichocyst pores (t), rows of 4 or 5 mucopores (m) and, knobs (k). E) apical region showing two pores, flagellar (fp) and auxiliary (ap). F) sagittal view of periflagellar region showing the "ear shaped" collar sheaths © with a periflagellar structure similar to that typified by Pertola et al., (2003), single tooth (s), forked tooth (f) and, ridged edge (re).

20.8 µm long and 7.5–10.8 µm wide (N=65). The valves are covered by small knobs (density 9–10 per µm²), sometimes interconnected by a ridge (Fig. 2 A–F). We observed two kind of pores: trichocysts and mucocysts, which bear different ornamentation on the inner and outer sides of the valves. The former present a triangular space on the outer side and are more prominent on the inner valve (Fig. 2B–D). The periflagellar region is very similar to that reported by Pertola *et al.*, 2003 for *P. minimum* [4], but in *P. donghaiense*, the flagellar and auxiliary pores are oval shaped (Figs. 2E). The features reported here, and others that were not reported in the original description of *P.*

• India

Karenia mikimotoi bloom in Arabian Sea

A harmful algal bloom (HAB) occurred from July to September 2004 on the Kerala coast of the Arabian Sea. *Karenia mikimotoi*, a dinoflagellate, accounted for nearly 98% of the standing crop of >20 µm fraction of phytoplankton. Mass mortality of fish coincided with the bloom event. Algal cell density peaked at 9.0×10^4 cells L^{-1} during the second week of September. Levels of PO_4^{3-} ($10.5 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$) and of Fe ($2 \text{ mg } L^{-1}$) were high compared to corresponding seasonal

donghaiense, has been submitted for publication [5].

P. trachodium has been observed 10 times in Mazatlán Bay, blooming in April 1980, November 1985, April 1986, July 1989, April 1990, March 1994, from March to August 1996, June 2000 and March 2003. *P. donghaiense* occurred only twice as the dominant organism, in April 1985 and April 1994; during March, April and May 1990 and 2000, it followed the dominant species *P. balticum*. For further biogeographical information, see reference [1].

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R. Cortés-Altamirano, UNAM, ICMYL-UAMazatlán, Apdo. 811, Mazatlán 82040, Sin., Mexico.
Email: robtiko@ola.icmyl.unam.mx.

A. Sierra-Beltrán, CIBNOR. Apdo. 128, 23000 La Paz, B.C.S., Mexico.
Email: asierra04@cibnor.mx.

Y. Hornelas Orozco, UNAM, ICMYL. Apdo. 70-305, 04510 D.F., Mexico.
Email: hornel@mar.icmyl.unam.mx.

Fig. 1. Location of algal bloom and sampling sites.

values of $0.5 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ and $0.2 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ respectively. Dissolved oxygen levels had dropped from 5.6 to $0.2 \text{ mg } L^{-1}$ by the end of the bloom. Covering of the gill lamellae by mucous released by the bloom and hypoxia following collapse of the bloom may have caused fish mortality. A noxious odour and respiratory problems among children on the coast were also noticed.

Bloom conditions were recorded from mid-July to mid-September 2004 off the coast of Thiruvananthapuram, west India, between latitudes $8^{\circ} 22' N$ - $8^{\circ} 34' N$ and longitudes $76^{\circ} 48' E$ - $76^{\circ} 59' E$. Six transects were established at 4 km intervals along the coast, at Puthenthura, Pallithura, Veli, Shangumugam, Muttathura, and Panattura, respectively from north to south (Fig. 1). On each transect, two stations were occupied, one near shore and one 25 km offshore, 25 km, as well as a few intermediate stations between these. Water samples were collected at all stations at 1 metre depth. Phytoplankton was sampled with a 20mm net and fixed with Lugol solution. Shellfish samples for toxin analysis were collected from the area, and stored frozen in the laboratory. Dead finfish strewn along the coast were also examined.

Standard physico-chemical procedures were followed [1]; 0.45μ filtered water samples were used for NO_2 , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} determinations following Brewer and Riley [2] and Grasshoff [3]. Iron was analyzed by the methylene blue method [4]. Chlorophyll a concentrations were determined by JGOFS protocol [1]. Species composition was determined in 1 ml subsamples: identifications were based on keys in UNESCO [5], Santhanam *et al* [6] and Hallegraeff *et al* [7].

The temperature of the water, when the bloom was first noticed on July 15 varied from $28.22^{\circ}C$ near shore to $28.52^{\circ}C$ offshore, and salinity from 33.9‰ near shore to 35.7‰ offshore. Dissolved oxygen levels varied from 0.2 to $5.6 \text{ mg } L^{-1}$. pH varied from 7.8 near shore to 8.2 offshore. Concentrations of PO_4^{3-} were abnormally high, $10.5 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ near shore and $5.0 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ offshore. Concentrations of NH_4^+ varied from $5.5 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ near shore to $4.2 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ offshore, nitrite from $0.2 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ near shore to $0.3 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ offshore, and NO_3^- concentrations were in the range of $4.8 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ near shore to $3.2 \mu\text{mol } L^{-1}$ offshore (Table 1).

Concentrations of iron were rather high, in the range of 2.7 near shore compared to $1.1 \text{ mg } L^{-1}$ offshore.

Table 1. Variations in Physiochemical conditions during July to September 2004.

	July 15		Sep 9		Sep 23	
	Near shore	Offshore	Near shore	Off shore	Near shore	Off shore
Temp (°C)	28.22	28.52	29.63	29.41	30.33	30.18
pH	7.8	8.2	8.1	8.3	8.4	8.3
Salinity (‰)	33.9	35.7	34.6	34.2	34.0	34.1
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	5.6	5.4	4.8	5.0	0.2	2.8
Phosphate (? mol L ⁻¹)	10.5	5.0	5.4	3.8	4.0	1.6
Ammonia (? mol L ⁻¹)	5.5	4.2	1.8	1.0	0.5	0.5
Nitrite (? mol L ⁻¹)	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.2
Nitrate (? mol L ⁻¹)	3.4	3.2	2.3	1.8	2.2	2.6

Predominant winds during the bloom period were onshore, southwesterly and westerly. Winds from the SW accounted for 32% and SSW for 22% of the total time, with wind speed and frequencies as follows: 1-5 kmph (0.8%), 6-10 kmph (1.2%), 11-15 kmph (27%), 16-20 kmph (65.5%), and 21-25 kmph (5%).

A total of 18 algal taxa consisting of 14 diatoms and 4 dinoflagellates were identified in the bloom. Diatoms included *Chaetoceros lorenzianus*, *Thalassionema nitzschioides*, *Thalassiosira eccentrica*, and *Skeletonema costatum*. Of the dinoflagellates present, *Karenia mikimotoi*, *Ceratium macroceros*, *Protoperidinium depressum* and *Prorocentrum micans*, *K. mikimotoi* accounted for >90% of the phytoplankton.

There was a conformity in phytoplankton abundance between near shore and offshore. For example at station Veli, the cell density was around $3.0 \times 10^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ near shore, and $2.0 \times 10^2 \text{ L}^{-1}$ offshore on July 15. By Sept 9, it had risen to $9.4 \times 10^4 \text{ L}^{-1}$ near shore and $4.4 \times 10^4 \text{ L}^{-1}$ offshore. By Sept 23, it had decreased to $2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ L}^{-1}$ near shore and $5.0 \times 10^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ offshore. Chlorophyll a increased from 8.8 mg m^{-3} in July 15 to 721 mg m^{-3} by Sept 9th, followed by a decrease; maximum chlorophyll values compare favorably with those reported in high density blooms elsewhere. The bloom-affected area was covered with slimy mucus, partly washed ashore.

The onshore and poleward winds do not lead to upwelling. In our study there was no increase in salinity, or decrease in temperature, which suggests absence of upwelling. The high concentrations of nutrients ($5.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1} \text{ NH}_3$, $10.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, PO_4^{3-} $2.7 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ Fe}$) can be attributed to heavy runoff. This was corroborated by unusually high precipitation (60 mm in two days) during

this period. Thus the explosive algal growth can be attributed to a sudden increase in nutrients from the land; the role of nutrients in the evolution of HAB has been documented [10]. Many HAB species display a preference for ammonia over other nitrogenous nutrients, as reflected in the present case, where NH_4^+ concentrations were high, whereas NO_2^- and NO_3^- were low [11].

As the bloom declined, a massive fish mortality of *Rastrelliger kanagurta*, *Sardinella longiceps*, *Arius arius*, *Seganus javus*, *Psettodes erumei*, *Monacanthus hispidus*, *Diodon hystrix*, and *Anguilla* sp. occurred. Examination of the dead fish revealed heavy mucous coatings on their gills. Fish kills are often marked with an odour resembling rotten eggs, characteristic of hydrogen sulphide (H_2S), and perceptible even at concentrations of 0.002 mg L^{-1} . It is highly toxic to most organisms. In the present studies, H_2S concentration reached 1.6 mg L^{-1} .

The presence of high concentrations of ammonia may have stressed the fish, affecting their metabolism and immunity responses. The situation was further aggravated by the anaerobic conditions with release of H_2S , as the bloom ended. Further, mucus released by algae during the bloom covered the gill filaments of the fish, leading to asphyxiation and death, consistent with the other reports.

The prevailing winds carried the putrid smell from the decline of the bloom and decaying fish towards the coast, along with H_2S released under anaerobic conditions. All these airborne contaminants resulted in irritation of eyes and nasal membranes, coughing, sneezing and in some cases even, asthmatic attack among the coastal population.

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C.S.P. Iyer, R.S. Robin, M.S. Sreekala & S. Shyam Kumar. Centre for Marine Analytical Reference & Standards (C-MARS) Regional Research Laboratory, Thiruvananthapuram 695019, Kerala, India.
Email: iyer_csp@yahoo.com.

• India

Microcystis aeruginosa bloom on Southwest coast of India

Photosynthetic prokaryotes like Cyanobacteria (blue green algae) are cardinal elements of aquatic ecosystems. Blue green algae proliferate quickly in stagnant lakes with high nutrient levels, during less turbulent warm seasons, resulting in 'blooms' that turn the water green, often with floating layers of green scum. Toxic blooms of cyanobacteria have been observed elsewhere in the aquatic ecosystems [1]. Several species of cyanobacteria produce both neurotoxins and hepatotoxins often causing health problems for humans and affecting standing crop of the finfishes. *Microcystis* is a prominent genus of toxic cyanobacteria. Morphologically a few species belonging to the genus form dense aggregations of cells floating on the surface of the water forming thick layer of green scum. Such growth can produce bad smell and affect the aesthetics of freshwater bodies and can be often lethal to livestock and humans [2].

The Chalakudy river is considered to be the lifeline of central Kerala. It originates from the Anamalai region, which is a collection of hills and the river transverse through Parambikulam, Kuriyarkutty, Sholayar, Karapara and Anakayam joining Periyar near Puthenvelikara, in the Ernakulam district emptying into the Arabian Sea at Azheekode. Chalakudy River performs a pivotal role in shaping the economic prospects of Kerala. It helps in power generation, domestic water supply, irrigation, tourism, Industrial production,

Fig. 2. *Microcystis* bloom.

collection of various inorganic resources and fisheries.

During the first week of March 2008, water discolouration of the river Chalakudy near the Kanakkankadavu regulator cum bridge (Fig. 1) was reported in the press. The surface water was green with floating layers of green scum (Fig. 2), spreading in an area of around 5 km². This regulator cum bridge, which prevents the entry of saline water from Cochin estuary into the river during the summer months, tend the locals to depend on this water for agricultural and domestic uses.

Detailed analysis of the samples revealed that the discolouration was due to *Microcystis aeruginosa* a Cyanophycean member (Fig. 3). *Microcystis* is one of the common algal species found in the river. This alga is capable of producing a hepatotoxin 'microcystin' which in high concentrations could be fatal to humans, livestock, and pets. However, only itching and irritation of the skin among the locals was reported. The physico chemical characteristics of the bloom area are shown in Table 1. *Microcystis* bloom samples were taken and preserved for the toxin analysis and molecular taxonomic studies.

Influence of nutrient contents in surface water receiving high radiation influences the abundance and distribution of phytoplankton. Lower reaches of Chalakudy river receive large quantities of effluents from domestic source and effluents from bone meal factory. The shutters and regulator dams raised during the premonsoon season prevents easy mixing of seawater from the highly saline Cochin estuary during the warm months to the Chalakkudy river. This is sure to increase the phosphorous content of the surface water where this nutrient will otherwise act as a limiting factor. This could be the reason for a bloom of the Cyanobacteria *Microcystis aeruginosa* during this period. It may be assumed that during the bloom the phytoplankton

Fig. 1 Map showing the *Microcystis* bloom area.

is quantitatively abundant and qualitatively poor resulting in low diversity. This situation according to Margalef (1978) represents the climax phytoplankton community structure the time frame of which is controlled by nutrient enrichment and change in N:P ratios.

The stagnant condition resulting from lack of flow of water might have resulted in a 'dystrophic' condition supporting large biomass of less number of species among which *Microcystis aeruginosa* occupied around 98% of the biomass.

Fig. 3. *Microcystis* cells x 100.

Table 1. Physicochemical parameters of *Microcystis* bloom area.

Parameter	Bloom area
Temperature (°C)	31
Salinity (ppt)	0
pH	8.4
Dissolved Oxygen (mg l ⁻¹)	6.28
Nitrate (μmol l ⁻¹)	4.11
Phosphate (μmol l ⁻¹)	8.147
Silicate (μmol l ⁻¹)	25.64
Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (mg m ⁻³)	23.4
Cell count (Cells m ⁻³)	4 x 10 ⁸

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K.B. Padmakumar¹, M.G. Sanilkumar², A.V. Saramma², V.N. Sanjeevan¹ & N.R. Menon²

¹Centre for Marine Living Resources and Ecology (CMLRE), Ministry of Earth Sciences, Govt. of India, Kochi, Kerala, India.

²Dept. of Marine Biology, Microbiology and Biochemistry, School of Marine Sciences, Cochin University of Science & Technology, Kochi, Kerala, India.

Email: kbpadmakumar@gmail.com

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GEOHAB Modeling Workshop

The Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (GEOHAB) program is planning a workshop to help integrate modeling activities into GEOHAB Core Research Projects (CRPs) and regional/national projects. The workshop will be open to any interested students and scientists, but the number of participants will be limited by the size of the meeting space. The workshop will be held at the Martin Ryan Institute, National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland on 15-19 June 2009. Inexpensive accommodations will be available on campus for students. The organizing committee for the workshop is chaired by Dennis McGillicuddy (USA); other members include Wolfgang Fennel (Germany), Marcel Babin (France), Marina Levy (France), Peter Franks (USA), Icarus Allen (UK), and Ken Furuya (Japan). CRP chairs Patrick Gentien, Grant Pitcher, Pat Glibert, and Allan Cembella have also participated in the planning. Information about the meeting is available at www.geohab-models.org.

Objectives

The objectives for the meeting will be to

- stimulate modeling activity in GEOHAB Core Research Projects (CRPs);
- entrain researchers at all levels (students, postdocs, faculty, etc.) into HAB modeling;
- facilitate dialog between model developers and HAB researchers involved in process studies through joint training sessions;
- improve understanding of HAB processes through linkage of models, *in situ* observations, and remote sensing;
- foster linkage between HAB modeling and the broader community of biogeochemical, ecosystem, and population dynamics modeling;
- highlight species-specific aspects intrinsic to HAB modeling: autecology, behavior, species interactions, toxin production, etc.;

- improve capabilities for prediction of HABs and quantitative assessment of their skill;
- encourage the use of advanced data assimilation techniques in HAB modeling;
- encourage the use of observing system simulation experiments (OSSEs) in array design;
- improve forecast products and their dissemination to maximize their benefit to the user community; and
- develop a written glossary for terminology.

Structure

The workshop will consist of four connected elements:

1. Plenary talks comprised of (a) invited reviews on HAB modeling and other relevant approaches (ecosystem modeling, population dynamics modeling), and (b) contributed talks on models and observations in support of the CRPs.
2. Dialogue seminars given by HAB observationalists and modelers. Specific modeling needs of the CRPs will be identified; implementation plans will be developed, utilizing existing modeling infrastructure where practical, and identifying needs for additional model development where gaps exist.
3. Tutorials and training on model design and application of models (geared toward students involved in CRPs).
4. Student mentoring.

Product

A set of peer-reviewed contributions will be published in a special issue of a suitable journal, such as *Journal of Marine Systems* or perhaps an open-access journal. The tentative title of the special issue is *Modeling biophysical interactions in harmful algal blooms: processes and methods*.

D. McGillicuddy, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, USA.
Email: dmcgillicuddy@whoi.edu

9th IOC-AECID-IEO Course on Harmful Phytoplankton

Picture of participants and teachers in the 2008 Vigo course.

The 9th IOC-AECID-IEO Course on Harmful Phytoplankton was held in the Oceanographic Centre of Vigo, Spain, in June 2008. Like in previous years, this course was jointly sponsored by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, the Spanish Agency of International Cooperation and Development (AECID) and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO).

The course focused on taxonomy of harmful marine microalgae, and was intended for Latin-American and African experts having experience in microalgae identification, responsible for setting up or strengthening their national or regional harmful marine microalgae monitoring programs.

For the first time in the Vigo Centre, the course had a distant learning part participants should complete before attending the classes held in Vigo. This distant learning was supported by the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae of Copenhagen. Jacob Larsen was the person in charge of its supervision, using the Absalon e-learning platform at the Copenhagen University. This part of the course comprised approximately 45 hours of individual learning and was

developed from 5th May – 6th June.

The second part of the course was held in Vigo from 11th to 27th June. It comprised 93 hours of lectures and practical sessions on the identification of harmful algae and cysts, as well as introductory lessons on marine biotoxins, monitoring and management of harmful events, chemical taxonomy and molecular tools, ecology of microalgae,

cultures and sampling techniques at sea and in the laboratory. Participants were also able to report on their national HAB events, exchanging impressions on their experience.

11 scientists from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, El Salvador, Peru, Spain and Venezuela attended the course.

This year we had the invaluable contribution of Jacob Larsen from IOC SCCHA, Denmark and Celia Villac from Universidade de Tabaté, Brazil, as guest teachers, as well as our usual collaborators for this kind of courses: Santiago Fraga, Isabel Bravo, Beatriz Reguera, Sonsoles González-Gil, Lourdes Velo, Francisco Rodríguez and Pilar Rial from the IEO, Vigo; José Franco, Beatriz Paz and Pilar Riobó from IIM-CSIC, Vigo; Yolanda Pazos and Fabiola Arévalo from INTECMAR, Vilagarcía de Arousa; María Rodríguez-Velasco from the EU-CRLMB, Vigo; Emilio Marañón from the Universidade de Vigo and Monica Lion from the IOC-IEO SCCHA, Vigo.

Participants contributed actively to the classes and we enjoyed a superb work atmosphere.

If you are interested in this kind of IOC training activities, please check our web site <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/> for complementary information.

Taxonomy practical class with Jacob Larsen.

GEOHAB

Global Ecology and Oceanography of
Harmful Algal Blooms

Second Asian GEOHAB Meeting

The Second Asian GEOHAB Meeting was held at the Institute of Oceanography in Nha Trang, Vietnam on Jan. 31–Feb. 1, 2008 as a sequel to the Asian GEOHAB Meeting held in Tokyo on March 15–16, 2007. The first meeting reviewed current activities on HAB issues in Asia with 20 presentations on a broad range of topics (fol.fs.a.u-tokyo.ac.jp/1stAsianGEOHAB/abstracts.pdf). The second meeting was more focused to identify key questions and research components for drafting a plan for the development of Asian GEOHAB to launch international cooperative research. The meeting was attended by more than 60 participants from 11 countries. Sixteen presentations were made and regional priority was well addressed. Species highlighted include *Prorocentrum donghaiense*,

Cochlodinium polykrikoides, *Karenia mikimotoi*, *Noctiluca scintillans*, *Pyrodinium bahamense* var *compressum*, *Alexandrium minutum*, *Dinophysis* spp., and benthic dinoflagellates. Most presentations focused on scientific aspects on ecology and oceanography of HABs; some presentations introduced on-going national and international projects in Asia. In addition, the urea dumping issue in the Sulu Sea, Philippines, was reviewed, and its ecological consequences relevant to HAB issues were discussed. The programme and abstracts of the meeting are available at http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/AsianHAB%20abstractBook_Latest_Lam.pdf.

After the presentation sessions, subgroups convened to identify specific questions that can be addressed in a

comparative context, and to recognize what it would take to address these questions including co-operative research, workshops, joint cruises and capacity building. Four subgroups were formed on 1) biogeography and biodiversity of HAB species, 2) nutrients and eutrophication, 3) adaptive strategies, and 4) comparative ecosystems. It was agreed to prepare a report of this meeting as a GEOHAB publication based on materials used in the presentations, and the discussion of the establishment of a GEOHAB regional program, HABs in Asia. An international editorial team was formed from participants to prepare a document on Asian GEOHAB.

K. Furuya, The University of Tokyo, Japan.

Email: furuya@fs.a.u-tokyo.ac.jp.

Ocean fertilization with urea

In late 2007 a private corporation based in Australia proposed enrichment of the Sulu Sea, Philippines, a region of high biodiversity, with thousands of tonnes of urea to stimulate algal blooms and sequester carbon.

Scientists in the Philippines immediately reacted when they learned about the project. They wrote letters to government officials and open letters published in local newspapers. In parallel, the international scientific community reacted promptly and from a GEOHAB meeting in Vietnam in January 2008, as well as other networking, emerged a view point paper with 57 authors for the 'Marine Pollution Bulletin' [1]. The paper outlined the scientific reasons why the proposal was flawed. These reasons were conveyed to the Philippine authorities.

The concern over urea enrichment to generate plankton blooms for carbon

credits is multifaceted. Urea is preferentially used as a nitrogen source by some cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates, many of which are neutrally or positively buoyant, making them less likely to sink to the deep sea. Biological pumps to the deep sea are classically leaky, and the inefficient burial of new biomass makes the estimation of a net loss of carbon from the atmosphere questionable at best. The potential for growth of toxic dinoflagellates is also high, as many grow well on urea and some even increase their toxicity when grown on urea. Many toxic dinoflagellates form cysts which can settle to the sediment and germinate in subsequent years, forming new blooms even without further fertilization. If large-scale blooms do occur, it is likely that they will contribute to hypoxia in the bottom waters upon decomposition. Lastly, urea

production requires fossil fuel usage, further limiting the potential for net carbon sequestration. The environmental and economic impacts are potentially great and need to be rigorously assessed.

This debate finally resulted in the rejection of the project by the Philippine authorities, however the parties behind the initiative are said to be seeking alternative locations.

The GEOHAB Scientific Steering Committee in April 2008 issued an Advisory Bulletin on Urea Fertilization, which can be found at the GEOHAB web site www.geohab.info.

References:

1. Glibert *et al* 2008. *Ocean urea fertilization for carbon credits poses high ecological risks*. *Mar Pollut Bull*, 56 (6): 1044–1056.

*H. Enevoldsen, IOC-UNESCO.
Email: h.enevoldsen@unesco.org*

ISSHA

ISSHA President's Corner

International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

As I write this on 8-8-08 my thoughts go toward China, the exciting happenings at the opening of the 2008 Summer Olympic Games and the army of athletes that will compete. In just a two short months a small army of phytoplanktologists, toxicologists, ecologists, oceanographers, public health officials, marine resource managers and remote sensing experts will also be arriving in China to enjoy the 13th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ISSHA). It will be held in Hong Kong from 3-5 November 2008. Please visit ISSHA's website to learn more about the exciting things the Co Organizers Prof. K. C. Ho and Prof. M. Zhou and Local Organizing Committee have planned for us.

Auction

The ISSHA Auction was one of the most popular events at the Copenhagen

Conference and it will be back by popular demand. The Auction is fast becoming a tradition. It is an opportunity for the Conference participants to bid on donated items that range from signed reprints, books, photos, micrographs or craftsmanship (paintings, drawings, carvings etc.), homemade wine, beer or other specialities. The auction items are donated by ISSHA members and sponsors from around the world and the proceeds are used for the benefit of ISSHA members. This year ISSHA was able to offer partial travel support to more than 25 students to attend the 13th Conference.

Prof. Barrie Dale will serve as the auctioneer and provocateur ensuring the evening will be exciting, fun filled and a bit over the top! Please help us make the 13th Conference auction a success. We need donations for the auction and only your imagination limits what can be

donated for this very worth effort. Please contact the secretariat at secretariat@hab2008.hk to provide a description of the items you plan to donate. There will be a list of items, updated frequently, at the ISSHA website www.issaha.org.

Election

ISSHA members will soon be receiving their ballot to elect new Officers and Council Members to lead ISSHA for the next 3 years. We are extremely pleased to offer an exceptional slate of candidates for the coming term and know you'll be inspired by their fine leadership. Take time to return your ballot and influence the future of the Society.

With best regards, I look forward to seeing in Hong Kong in November,

*Pat Tester, ISSHA President.
Email: pat.tester@noaa.gov*

Future events

OCTOBER 2008

Ciguatera and Related Biotoxins Workshop

Nouméa, New Caledonia, 21-31 October 2008.

A workshop on the latest developments in ciguatera research, covering environmental influences, causative organisms and socio-economic and medical aspects.

First call-tentative programme covers: toxinogenesis, environmental influences, chemistry of involved ciguatoxins, clinical treatment and folk remedies, toxicology and mechanisms of action, ciguateric fish species, socio-economic impacts, collection and use of clinical and epidemiological data, and risk assessment and management.

Additional info: www.ird.nc/ciguatera

JUNE 2009

7th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety

Nantes, France, 14-19 June 2009.

Programme will include epidemiology, risk assessment, toxin monitoring, analytical methods in microbiology and biochemistry, health consumer protection, management of farming/harvesting areas, post-harvest treatment, and macro-economic analysis of the repercussions of shellfish-farming crises. This conference will be an exciting forum for scientists, regulators and producers, which will make an important contribution to limiting health risks associated with microbiological, toxic and chemical contamination of coastal areas. The conference will also address the identification of chemical contaminants and target species that represent significant risks for consumers. Finally, it will aim to improve the development of high performance detection tools to prevent and/or monitor contamination, and will thereby contribute to supporting existing marine environment monitoring networks.

Important dates:

- Abstracts submission: 15 Dec, 08.
- Abstract authors notified of selection: 1 Feb, 09.

- Early registration price: until 15 Mar, 09.
- Normal registration price: 16 Mar–29 Apr.
- Late registration price: from 30 Apr, 09.
- Deadline for online hotel reservation: May 11, 09.
- Deadline for online registration and correspondence: Jun 1, 09.

P. Lassus, ICMSS09 organiser and host. Email: icmss09@ifremer.fr

See you in Hong Kong at the 13th International Conference on Harmful Algae!

3-7 November 2008
www.hab2008.hk

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

Compiled and edited by Tim Wyatt, Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas, CSIC, Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo, Spain; Tel.: +34 986 23 19 30/23 19 73; Fax: +34 986 29 27 62; E-mail: twyatt@iim.csic.es and Mónica Lion, Centro Científico y de Comunicación sobre Algas Nocivas COI-IEO, Apdo. 1552, 36200 Vigo, Spain; Tel.: +34 986 49 21 11; Fax: +34 986 49 20 03; E-mail: monica.lion@vi.ieo.es

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Project Coordinator: Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen, Øster Farimagsgade 2D, DK-1353 Copenhagen K, Denmark Tel.: +45 33 13 44 46; Fax.: +45 33 13 44 47, E-mail: h.enevoldsen@unesco.org